

MAIN FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF INFORMATIVE TEXTS

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Abstract. This thesis discusses about the some of the features of translation and their usage in informative texts also deals with the peculiarities of translation of informative texts. In fact, in the field of translation we often make a distinction between informative and literary translation in a rather arbitrary, but not entirely incorrect, fashion. On top of that, unlike in literary translation, creativity is not really required, but precision is essential as every professional translator knows. And in this thesis the reader can obtain some knowledge about some of the characteristics of informative translation and their importance in translation process.

Informative translation refers to the rendering of non-literary texts to accurately and clearly convey facts and information to a target audience, prioritizing the message's authenticity over emotional or aesthetic impact. These translations are characterized by plain language, logical structure, and objective tone, serving functions like press reports, business documents, and technical manuals.

The informative text differs from expressive text and operative text. The words for expressive texts are "emotion" and "attitude". Compared with informative text, this type of text is clearly formal-oriented when translating. The operative text is to appeal to the recipient of the text, and the point is to infect the reader. For instance, advertising and election speech are designed to attract the audience or readers. The translation may pay attention to the following translation principles: plain, objective, logical, consistent, accurate and clear, and remember to avoid expressing personal emotions.

Having said that, different functions of the text, Newmark divided the text into three types: expressive texts, informative texts and vocative texts in his book *Approaches to Translation* in 1981. Expressive texts emphasize the authority of the original author. In translation, we should follow the principle of "original author first", which is faithful to both the ideological content expressed by the original author and the language style of the original author. Typical expressive texts include imaginative literary works; authoritative remarks and texts that do not need to consider the reader group and are the personal emotional catharsis of the author. The core of informative texts is the authenticity of content, and the author's language is secondary. In translation, the principle of "authenticity first" should be observed. The translator should take the language level of the target language readers as the standard in language application and strive to be straightforward to understand. Informational texts are commonly used in industry, agriculture, commerce, science, technology and economy, also their forms are often very standardized. The vocative texts take readers as the center and calls on readers to act, think and feel. Notices, product manuals, brochures and advertisements all fall into this category. The translator should make full use of the benefits of the target language and not stick to the expression form of the original text.

The basics of the informative function of language is external situation, the facts of any topic, reality outside language, including reported ideas or theories. For the aim of translation, typical informative¹ texts are concerned with any topic of knowledge, but texts about literary subjects, as they often express value-judgments, are apt to lean towards expressiveness. The format of an informative text is often standard: a textbook, a technical report, an article in a

newspaper or a periodical, a scientific paper, a thesis, minutes or agenda of a meeting. One normally assumes a modern, non-regional, non-class, non-idiolectal style, with perhaps four points on a scale of language varieties:

1. Formal, non-emotive, technical style for academic papers, characterized in English by passives, present and perfect tenses, literal language, jargon, multi-noun compounds with empty verbs, no metaphors;

2. Neutral or informal style with defined technical terms for textbooks characterized by first person plurals, present tenses, dynamic active verbs, and basic conceptual metaphors;

3. Informal warm style for popular science or art books (e.g. coffee-table books), characterized by simple grammatical structures, a wide range of vocabulary to accommodate definitions and numerous illustrations, and stock metaphors and a simple vocabulary;

4. Familiar, racy, non-technical style for popular journalism, characterized by surprising metaphors, short sentences, unconventional punctuation, adjectives before proper names and colloquialisms.

First and foremost, English is also to have a greater variety and distinctiveness in these styles, however it is lexically the product of several language groups (Saxon, Norse, French, Classical), and has a close contact with a wide variety of other languages; carried all over the world, it became the main carrier for technology and had little authoritative pressure exercised on its growth, apart from a short period in the eighteenth century. Notwithstanding, note two points: informative texts constitute the vast majority of the staff translator's work in international organizations, multi-nationals, private companies and translation agencies. Secondly, a high proportion of such texts are poorly written and sometimes inaccurate, and it is usually the translator's job to 'correct' their facts and their style. Thus, in spite of the hoary adages ('translation is impossible', etc.), the majority of translations nowadays are better than their originals - or at least ought to be so.

The importance and uniqueness of informative texts need translators to have extensive knowledge and profound cultural heritage, and flexibly use different translation strategies in translation. Communicative translation theory not only respects the original text, but also takes full account of the cultural register and language characteristics of the target language to ensure the fluency of communication, which is guiding significance for the translation practice of informative texts.

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